

D6.1 Rules of Operation for the Selection Committee

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- PU: Public
- PP: Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission)
- RE: Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission)
- CO: Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission)

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

RDA	Research Data Alliance
FAIR ¹	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable (set of principles)
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
HEIs	Higher Education Institutions
SC	Selection Committee
WG	Working Group
WP	Work Package

¹ <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>

Executive Summary

RDA TIGER supports RDA Working Groups (WG) to reach their full potential by facilitating their activities across aspects of the WG life-cycle. The project has assigned a budget for support for RDA WGs and third party grants to support the uptake of RDA TIGER services and to enhance and consolidate the work of the RDA WGs. In-kind support and grants will be offered during the lifetime of RDA TIGER. Procedures need to be established to ensure that all applications are processed and appraised appropriately, and budgetary decisions and grant allocations are examined and evaluated in a fair and transparent manner. These procedures will be led by WP6 with the support of the Selection Committee (SC).

Responsibility for grant approval and RDA WG selection for in-kind support lies with the RDA TIGER Selection Committee. This deliverable is a guidance document that sets out the rules of participation that the Committee should follow. It describes the types of funding instruments, rules that the decision making for WGs should follow including defining the selection criteria and role of the Selection Committee. It connects strongly to the work of WP1, the RDA TIGER Management work package in RDA TIGER who are responsible for the contractual elements of the grants and budget coordination.

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1. Scope of the Selection Committee

RDA TIGER has assigned a budget to a) indirectly support the RDA Working Groups (WGs) and b) directly support via a budget for third-party grants to support the uptake of RDA TIGER services and to enhance and consolidate the work of the RDA WGs. The in-kind support and grants will be offered during the lifetime of RDA TIGER. Procedures need to be in place to ensure that activities are carried out in a neutral and transparent manner, that all applications are dealt with fairly and that any budgetary decisions and grant allocations are consistently examined and evaluated. To meet these needs, a Selection Committee will be established to guide the management of the third-party grants and to put in place approval processes for the decision to support RDA WGs.

The Selection Committee consists of the following members:

- All RDA TIGER WP leads (one per WP).
- One Individual from the EOSC Association. The overarching aim of RDA TIGER is to contribute to the Horizon Europe EOSC partnership², thus having an EOSC Association member concretises these activities.
- Individuals from two of RDA's governing bodies: the Technical Advisory Board (TAB)³ and RDA Secretariat⁴. The RDA TAB provides technical expertise to the RDA Council and has been chosen for having presence on the SC as the TAB is directly responsible for the development and review of the RDA's WG.

The Committee has oversight of all the calls over the course of their life-time. It manages the call text preparation and selection criteria, and acts as the evaluation body for the applications. It is the remit of the committee to deal with grant allocation, timeframes, and monitoring the ongoing grants. Discussing scope for new calls is also part of its remit, and the committee has the freedom to adjust the budget between the planned calls.

Preparatory tasks before the committee meets will ensure that the members are presented in a timely way with decisions needed to be taken. The committee will meet quarterly for 90 minutes to take evaluation decisions and discuss the budget and new calls. Email communication is also expected in between meetings.

² <https://eosc.eu/partnership>

³ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/about-rda/our-leadership/rda-technical-advisory-board.html>

⁴ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/secretariat/>

2. Members of the Selection Committee (2023)

The following table details the members of the committee at its launch. **Change of members:** This is possible among the membership body they represent, on a yearly basis, with discussion with the Selection Committee (SC) members.

Table 1. RDA TIGER Selection Committee (SC) Members

RDA TIGER Project Members	
RDA TIGER WP1 (Coordination)	Ari Asmi (RDA AISBL) Chair of the SC
RDA TIGER WP2 (Communications)	Alexandra Delipalta (RDA AISBL)
RDA TIGER WP3 (Landscaping)	Laura Molloy (CODATA)
RDA TIGER WP4 (Outputs)	Ingrid Dillo (DANS)
RDA TIGER WP5 (Facilitation)	Ari Asmi (RDA AISBL)* ⁵
RDA TIGER WP6 (Quality Control)	Najla Rettberg (RDA AISBL)
Expert Member	Carlos Martinez Ortiz (Netherlands eScience Center)
EOSC ASSOCIATION	
	Karel Lubyen (President, EOSC Association)
RDA Technical Advisory Board	
	Raphael Cobe (Sao Paulo State University, TAB member)
	Isabelle Perseil (INSERM, TAB co-chair)
RDA Secretariat	
	Connie Clare (RDA Secretariat)

⁵ This position will change following completion of recruitment for the RDA AISBL for WP5.

3. Types of RDA TIGER support actions

3.1 Support Instruments

There are four types of support foreseen in the RDA TIGER project life-time. The following table describes the types of grants that will be utilised within the project, as well as the financial instruments involved⁶.

Table 2. RDA TIGER Grant Instruments

Type	Description	Provider (also the recipient of any direct monetary grant)	Type of financial instrument	Initial Budget ⁷
1. RDA WG In-kind support	RDA TIGER staff provide specific WG support (WPs 2,3,4,5).	RDA TIGER project partner(s)	In-kind (personnel costs) Process of Selection via Open Call.	85 PMs for facilitation, 36 PMs for communications
2. Direct Working Group grants	Funds given directly to WG group or its members as a reimbursement or by directly paying a service provider.	WG members, service providers (e.g. catering company, airline, hotel).	Reimbursements, invoices (for consumables, travel, etc.)	EUR 25,000 for travel grants, up to EUR 28,000 for meeting costs
3. Subcontracting grants	Subcontracting involves outsourcing a piece of work to outside entities in a predefined way as agreed at the start of the activity funded to be carried out, in order to support the WG. The subcontracts do not usually deal with the core activity of the WG.	Subcontractors are hired with a direct commercial contract in WP1. Subcontractors are not members of the WG. Subcontracting does not require an open call.	Subcontracting agreement (subcontracting).	EUR 23,000
4. Third party grants	A grant that is awarded as part of a competitive open call application process and can be defined in the duration of the project. These grants support the core activity of the WG work.	The winner of the open call application process, which can be a WG member or an external entity. The open call application process involves quality-based selection and a specific third party contract following the relevant ANNEX ⁸ .	Third party contract (third party grants) Process of Selection via Open Call.	EUR 300,000

⁶ Horizon Europe distinguishes between various types of financial instruments; RDA TIGER will use both subcontracting and third-party support grants. See also: <https://eufunds.me/what-is-the-difference-between-subcontracting-and-financial-support-to-third-parties-in-horizon-europe/> (accessed 29 March, 2023)

⁷ The budgets are set in the Description of Work, but can be moved between categories via Amendment process with the permission of the Granting Authority, also considering the potential available budget changes due to inclusion of indirect costs for the travel support costs.

⁸ This refers to the “Annex to the Application Form (HE CASE) Financial support to third parties version 1.0 July 2021” included in the Grant agreement of the RDA TIGER project.

The grants will be used to support the RDA WGs in different ways:

- 1. RDA WG In-kind support (inc. facilitation):** This is *in-kind* RDA TIGER support over the lifetime of the RDA WG and is the main support mechanism provided by the RDA TIGER project. This type of support grant does not have a separate budget line; the resources are part of the RDA TIGER direct personnel budget and the support is provided by the employees of the RDA TIGER partners. The application for support is subject to an evaluation process within the Selection Committee, which selects Groups to be supported based on the priorities of the RDA TIGER project (see Chapter 5). Support approval includes access to the other in-kind support mechanisms, such as communication, output and landscape analysis support, if needed and desired by the RDA WG. The RDA WGs can apply, via the application process, to receive this support *at any stage of their WG*. The main expectation is, however, that most of the RDA TIGER supported WGs will have this support from the very beginning of their work to the end of their operations.
- 2. Direct WG grants:** These grants provide WG members and the group itself direct support via small grants paid either as reimbursements or directly to service providers (e.g., catering companies, airlines, etc.) from the RDA TIGER partner budget (direct costs for subcontracting/purchase/other costs). Direct WG Grants are intended to support WG activities (e.g., meetings and workshops). These grants are small in size (EUR 5,000) and are typically limited to travel grants or meeting/workshop organisation costs (e.g., catering, room hire, etc.)
- 3. Subcontracting grants:** These grants provide WGs with expertise or services that are beyond the capabilities, available time and/or resources available within the *in-kind* support provided by RDA TIGER. Working groups may identify a specific service required to further their activities; specialist service providers will then be selected and contracted by the RDA Association to conduct the relevant work within the available budget for subcontracting. These grants are: a) subcontracted to external entities (outside of the WG and the RDA TIGER Consortium); and, b) of small budget (less than EUR 5,000). Examples of these services may include WG coordination work, data collection and analyses (e.g., surveys), gap and landscape analyses, formalisation of results, technical harmonisation for selected standards, report writing and text editing.
- 4. Third-party grants:** These grants provide substantial financial support (up to EUR 60,000) for contracting of third parties (external to RDA TIGER partners) in order to support core WG activities. Such grants can be used for, but are not limited to, recommendation and output development and testing, complex technical and policy implementation, and for promoting the adoption of WG recommendations and outputs by enabling their demonstration and implementation in real-world settings. Third-party grants have an open call application process and use the 'Financial support to Third Parties' budget line of the RDA Association. The open call mechanism, along with its formal and transparent evaluation process, follows the rules set out in this document and the relevant Annex of the Grant Agreement. Third-party grants can be given to

any party which provides capability to provide this service, including WG members⁹. Due to the competitive nature of the open call application process, there is no guarantee that any specific entity will receive the advertised grant. If the needs are very specific to the WG, it is recommended that the WG defines the third-party grant carefully to ensure that the third-party awarded the grant will be capable of delivering the expected service. All normal eligible costs can be covered, such as personnel time, travel and workshop facilitation. Further subcontracting of a third-party Grant is not permitted. In accordance with EC specifications, no applicant can receive more than EUR 60,000 from a third-party grant within the RDA TIGER project.

Figure 1. Process of Grants and Contracts Supported by RDA TIGER. All applications are handled by the Selection Committee which assigns the available resources to the WG support. Depending on the support type, these are either directly assigned to service providers (WPs 2-5), directly used for the WG support in WP1 minor grants, or specified for external experts/groups via either subcontracting (WP1) or via Third party open call mechanisms (WP6). The last type of grants have additional review/selection steps for the providers, and additional contracting with the partners. Optionally, the Selection Committee can also require post-grant reviews from the Third party grants.

⁹ Non-EU parties applicability still needs to be confirmed from the new PO in Commission - situation 2023-03-27

4. Call Management Process

4.1 Rolling Calls

Figure 2. WP6 Timeline and workflow

The calls for WG group support and funded support will be open on a rolling basis and will be continuously promoted throughout the life of RDA TIGER. Applications are received all year around. There will be four cut-off dates (May, August, November and February) during each year of the RDA TIGER project, also made clear in the proposal. At these dates, WP6 will collect the proposals, check them for eligibility, divide them into the call types, and send them to the Selection Committee. The committee will meet two weeks later for a dedicated meeting of 90 minutes and make decisions of which grants to fund.

Figure 2 presents the timeline, process and workflow led by WP6 and indicates where the Steering Committee is involved in the process.

Figure 3. RDA TIGER Grant Life-Cycle Management

4.2 Publication of the calls

The calls will be published on the RDA TIGER website. To simplify the process, it is envisaged that two call-types are published, one for in-kind RDA WG support and another for financial support. It is up to the grant committee to assess what type of funding instrument they should receive, although the applicants are recommended to specify instruments in the applications.

The calls are continuously open, with set dates for 'cut off' and evaluation and grant approval. They will be permanently displayed on the RDA TIGER website and the respective evaluation dates will be updated quarterly. The calls are widely and periodically advertised by WP2 in relevant RDA platforms, EOSC related activities (in particular using the EOSC partnership platforms), and on social media.

Once the text of the call has been agreed and drafted, a copy will be circulated among the RDA TIGER consortium for input. In the case of a call for third-party support, the call text will specify the title of the call, the available budget, deadline and the expected duration of the service provided. Guidelines for submission of the application will also be provided.

Calls will be published with the information and according to a set template as described in Table 3.

Table 3. RDA TIGER Calls: general information

Elements of the Call	Comments on each element
Start Date / cut-off date	<i>Calls are generally open until the end of the project</i>
Dates for evaluation via the selection committee (four times a year), and the last date to submit an application to be evaluated in a specific session	<i>Decisions on new grants are made on specific dates with necessary time to prepare for the decisions (de-facto application deadline)</i>
Financial Support / Maximum per grant per activity	<i>These are set by the budget situation, and can be updated after each approval round</i>
Eligibility Criteria	<i>Applicants cannot be part of the RDA TIGER Consortium or Selection Committee, and any conflicts of interest should be flagged.</i>
Description of what the call is looking for	<i>Description of the RDA TIGER grant types and any specific additions or clarifications to the original call texts.</i>
Maximum number of awards available per grant on the next evaluation round	<i>This is set by the Selection Committee beforehand, if there is a need to limit the number of applicants due to resource limitations.</i>
How to apply	<i>At the start of the process, and for in-kind applicants only, the procedure will involve sending a .pdf to a specified email address. For other calls, more secure mechanisms will be developed.</i>
Evaluation Criteria and listing of categories how the calls will be assessed (see section 5.1)	<i>The evaluation criteria should be clearly stated in the application process and additional contact points should be identified for the applicants, if they need further help. For financial grant mechanisms, this information can also be given by the assigned facilitator (if they are recipients of that in-kind service).</i>

<p>Disclaimer: no institution or individual can receive more than EUR 60,000</p>	<p><i>In accordance with the Horizon 2020 financial regulations, no individual or organisation (third party) will be awarded more than EUR 60,000 (sixty thousand Euro). Explicitly, a third party may apply and be awarded funding in different calls, but only be contracted for a total of EUR 60,000. If the limit is reached, no further contracts can be awarded to that individual or organisation (third party). This disclaimer is intended to warn candidates not to exceed this limit in their applications.</i></p>
<p>Timeline</p>	<p><i>Specify dates for next evaluation and timeline for informing successful awardees.</i></p>

4.3 Communication of the call

The RDA TIGER Communications Service will support the dissemination of the call in all respective channels, including the RDA community network and its multipliers (for example, the regional assembly). The calls will also be published on the EOSC Association website. Communication will intensify towards the quarterly evaluation periods to ensure maximum visibility across the RDA community.

4.4 Call application form

The call publication will specify a template to submit the call. The fields to be completed will include the following:

Table 4. RDA TIGER Calls: application form details for In-Kind Support

	Form	Comments
1	Contact details of the applicant	
2	The type of Support or Grant applied for: WG in-kind Support, WG grant, Other WG financial support.	<i>These can be moved from one category to another.</i>
3	Please outline your current RDA involvement e.g current RDA Group involvement	
4	Abstract of the application and what they want to achieve during the grant lifetime.	<i>Fixed word count (200 words).</i>
5	Impact: Please outline the concrete output your project will achieve with a contribution to any of the following initiatives: EOSC ecosystem and/or the SRIA ¹⁰ , International data-sharing initiatives, Implementation of the FAIR principles, RDA's strategic plan ¹¹ . Outline any applicable sustainability plans for the work foreseen.	
6	<p>Impact: Please describe how the output contributes to one or more of the following areas:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mechanisms and tools for creation, sharing, management and re-use of research outputs (e.g. data, software, publications, workflows, protocols, and methodologies); - Facilitating scientific multidisciplinary cooperation; <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Efficient handling or providing seamless access to large volumes of research outputs; - - Increasing FAIRness, openness and quality of scientific research in Europe and globally; 	

¹⁰ <https://eosc.eu/sria-mar>

¹¹ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/about-rda/rda-strategic-plan-2020-2023>

	- Creation of more meaningful monitoring and research evaluation mechanisms, enabling better reproducibility, validation and re-use of research outputs, or improving pathways for communication of science to the public	
7	Implementation: Explain how the work foreseen will be able to produce the required tasks, determined by the WG plan and idea. Include any information on the past activities in RDA of the applicant members (e.g. RDA, EOSC, Open Science expertise). Detail if the WG will cover major European and non-European initiatives and include experts relevant to the output creation.	
8	Acceptance of RDA's Guiding principles	<i>Tick box and link to: https://www.rdalliance.org/about-rda</i>
9	Gender information m/f/prefer to self-describe	<i>The RDA Grants Selection Committee is committed to providing a fair and transparent process in assessing all calls. The criteria established aim to provide a balanced geographical, gender and domain representation. For that reason we are collecting this information and in line with RDA's Privacy Policy.</i>
10	Personal data usage information and approval	<i>Short text explaining how personal data is used and protected during the evaluation</i>

Table 5. RDA TIGER Calls: application form details - Third Party Grants

	Form	Comments
1	Contact details of the applicant	
2	The type of Support or Grant applied for: WG in-kind Support, WG grant, Other WG financial support.	<i>These can be moved from one category to another</i>
3	Please outline your current RDA involvement e.g current RDA Group involvement	
4	Abstract of the application and what they want to achieve during the grant lifetime	<i>Fixed word count (200 words)</i>
5	Impact: Please outline the Expected impact and importance of the proposed additional work (e.g. adoption case or technical development), in the context of the expected WG outputs and the overall landscape the WG operates in. Third party grants with significant importance to the WG success (or impact) are prioritised, as well ones which push the overall WG subject areas beyond the current state-of-art	
6	Impact: Please clarify the work plan with milestones and clear aims.	
7	Implementation: Explain how the resources will be allocated (personnel months etc)	
8	Acceptance of RDA's Guiding principles	Tick box and link to: https://www.rdalliance.org/about-rda

<p>9</p>	<p>Gender information m/f/prefer to self-describe</p>	<p>“The RDA Grants Selection Committee is committed to providing a fair and transparent process in assessing all calls. The criteria established aim to provide a balanced geographical, gender and domain representation. For that reason we are collecting this information and in line with RDA’s Privacy Policy.</p>
<p>10</p>	<p>Personal data usage information and approval</p>	<p>Short text explaining how personal data is used and protected during the evaluation</p>

Table 6. RDA TIGER Calls: application form details - Smaller WG grants

	Form	Comments
1	Contact details of the applicant	
2	The type of Support or Grant applied for: WG in-kind Support, WG grant, Other WG financial support.	<i>These can be moved from one category to another</i>
3	Please outline your current RDA involvement e.g current RDA Group involvement	
4	Impact: Please explain the importance and impact of the added grant to the WG performance, in context of new developments, added connectivity (esp. International connectivity), or higher impact of the WG outputs.	
5	Implementation: Explain how the resources will be allocated (personnel months etc)	
6	Acceptance of RDA's Guiding principles	Tick box and link to: https://www.rdalliance.org/about-rda
7	Gender information m/f/prefer to self-describe	"The RDA Grants Selection Committee is committed to providing a fair and transparent process in assessing all calls. The criteria established aim to provide a balanced geographical, gender and domain representation. For that reason we are collecting this information and in line with RDA's Privacy Policy.
8	Personal data usage information and approval	Short text explaining how personal data is used and protected during the evaluation

Call page will include these forms in either a readily editable form (e.g. Word- or RTF file), or as a webform.

4.5 Application submission process

The first set of in-kind applications will be collected via a webform¹² set up on the RDA website. Requirements gathering for such a submission system as well as security issues will be discussed by the selection Committee for subsequent calls.

All calls will be screened for eligibility by WP1 and WP6 teams in order to:

- Check applications are complete;
- Ensure no member of the RDA TIGER consortium or Selection Committee has applied.

All Selection Committee members are required to sign a Non-Disclosure Agreement to be able to have access to applications. This NDA is presented in Annex 2 of this deliverable.

¹² <https://www.rd-alliance.org/rda-tiger-call-facilitation>

5. Evaluation of applications.

Each application will be assessed according to strict criteria, regardless of the support instrument that will be offered. Each criterion should be measurable, either qualitatively or quantitatively. Emphasis will be on quantitative measures to avoid any unclarity. Applicants will have to adhere to a certain number of criteria and then be given a corresponding score. The average score will be divided by the number of evaluators. Some aspects (e.g excellence) will be weighted. The scores can be made available to the applicants on demand. In general, the decision is final on the outcomes and where possible a short constructive feedback will be given with possibility for re-application in the next round.

5.1 Criteria for scoring

5.1.1 Priorities of the in-kind applications

The scoring of the in-kind applications is based on the similar process for scoring the Third Party applications (specified in the Grant Agreement), with the following adjustments based on the priorities of the RDA TIGER proposal. The overall scoring mechanisms are described in the Annex 1 of this deliverable.

1) **WG Output:**

Create outputs leading directly or indirectly to standards, recommendations, and methodologies essential for putting FAIR principles into practice or supporting the development of the EOSC ecosystem. Each supported WG should have output(s) with a clear connection to the EOSC or Open Science principles (e.g., the FAIR principles), such as an internationalisation or standardisation action based on an existing EOSC output (e.g., from existing or past EC-funded projects); and/or responding to an EOSC priority (e.g., in the EOSC Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda SRIA7 and its updates); or connecting via some other demonstrable pathway to the wider EOSC or Open Science needs.

2) **WG Impacts:**

The expected WG output should be connected to significant advance in **one or more** of the following impact areas:

- A. Mechanisms and tools for creation, sharing, management and re-use of research outputs (e.g. data, software, publications, workflows, protocols, and methodologies);
- B. Facilitating scientific multidisciplinary cooperation;
- C. Efficient handling or providing seamless access to large volumes of research outputs;
- D. Increasing FAIRness, openness and quality of scientific research in EUROpe and

globally;

- E. Creation of more meaningful monitoring and research evaluation mechanisms, enabling better reproducibility, validation and re-use of research outputs, or improving pathways for communication of science to the public.

3) WG Implementation and international connectivity

Ability of the WG to produce the required tasks, determined by the WG plan and idea, information on the past activities in RDA of the applicant members (e.g. RDA, EOSC, Open Science expertise). WGs expected existing or potential members covering major European and non-European initiatives and experts relevant to the output creation.

4) Resource availability and diversity

Due to limited amount of in-kind resources, the Selection Committee can prioritise groups which work in specific areas which have either more specialist in-kind services available (e.g. CODATA facilitators concentrate on policy-oriented facilitation, and NL eScienceCenter concentrates on research software oriented groups), or which demonstrate a facet of the RDA activities that are novel, or which have not yet received any RDA TIGER support actions.

5.1.2. Priorities for request of Third party grants

These are not the priorities of how recipients of the Third party call are chosen, but instead present the prioritisation on opening and resourcing requests for such calls.

1) **Impact:** Expected impact and importance of the proposed additional work (e.g. adoption case or technical development), in the context of the expected WG outputs and the overall landscape the WG operates in. Third party grants with significant importance to the WG success (or impact) are prioritised, as well ones which push the overall WG subject areas beyond the current state-of-art.

2) **Clarity of the goals of the Third party grant and applicability for opening a call.** The call requests should be clear and easy to advertise and have clear indicators on how to prioritise potential call respondents. Calls with clear statements of work, set milestones or aims, and indicators of types of entities which could succeed in the tasks are prioritised over ones which do not have these qualifiers.

3) **Request for the financial amount is realistic and within the available resources.** The SC can adjust the amounts if needed during their approval process

5.1.3 Priorities for the smaller WG-related grants (travel & meetings, subcontracting):

1) **Added value of the grant to the WG goals.** Importance and impact of the added grant to the WG performance, in the context of new developments, added connectivity (esp. International connectivity), or higher impact of the WG outputs.

2) **Excellence of the original WG goals.** This evaluation can be done separately, or be a part of earlier (or simultaneous) application to the in-kind evaluation. Higher scoring (and thus higher expected impact) WGs have priority to these grants.

3) **Request for the financial amount is realistic and within the available resources.** The SC can adjust the amounts if needed during their approval process.

6. Contractual Management

The Selection Committee will inform WP1 by email or other agreed communication mechanism (e.g., the Asana platform) to point to the outcomes of the quarterly round. The RDA AISBL will manage the contracts and the schedule for the payments. The RDA TIGER coordination in WP1 will follow on from the email informing the candidates.

Three agreements are foreseen:

1. Agreement to facilitate a RDA WG. This is not a contract but a set of terms and conditions that the facilitator will be giving the WG.
2. Contractual agreements with third party grantees e.g consultants
3. Agreement that individuals will have expenses paid and details about the reimbursement process.

7. Publication of the outcomes

The successful candidates will be informed by the selection committee via a central email account. Terms for their grant will be set out in this email.

The results of a) the RDA WGs to be facilitated and b) the groups with third party grants will be published on the RDA TIGER webpage.

8. Management of the Selection Committee

8.1 Scope of the meetings

The committee will meet four times a year for a minimum of 90 minutes. The agenda will be as follows:

1. Presentation of the state of play for the calls (running calls, calls due, extra calls to be opened)
2. Presentation of each of the calls to be screened
3. Discussion on each of the applications.
4. Ranking of third party grant applications
5. Decision making and preparation of grants awarded
6. Date of next meeting

Conflict of interest statements will need to be prepared by the Selection Committee in the case one is identified on each call. The Selection Committee will act as evaluators. Staff working on the RDA TIGER project are not eligible to receive grants, however members of

their organisation who are involved in relevant RDA WGs supported by facilitation are eligible. However they should flag up this connection if this occurs.

8.2 Preparation of the meetings

The RDA TIGER WP1 and WP6 will coordinate the preparation for the meetings. The date will be set at least two months in advance. All “rolling applications” will be collected into a shared drive and shared with the committee who are asked before the meeting to analyse the quarterly applications.

9. Monitoring of the calls

The calls will have to submit lightweight progress reports, and awardees will not be expected to complete timesheets. Each call will have a ‘manager’ assigned to ensure continuous communication with awardees. It is likely this will be the RDA TIGER WG Facilitator as they manage the WG over the life-cycle and any associated grants. For the other grants for WGs that don’t have facilitators, members of the Selection Committee will be allocated.

9.1 Final delivery and short reports

It is the responsibility of the facilitator to monitor any grants awarded to the RDA TIGER WG. The selection committee will decide by consensus if the delivered activity has responded adequately to the call. The activities will have a clear connection to the service quality task in WP6 and will be monitored according to quality benchmarks. It also depends on the payment schedule. In the case of small grants, the payment will happen at the start (under EUR 5,000). For larger grants or sub-contracting grants, there will be mid-term and end-term payment.

Table 7 . Required reporting per RDA TIGER grant type

Type of Grant	Formal reporting required
WG Support	Associated with mid-term report, a short report to be presented at the Selection Committee meetings
Direct WG Grant	Short report or blog on use of resources e.g travel grant event blog is expected

Sub-Contracting Grant or Third-Party Grant

For any sub-contracting or third-party grant, a short final report will be submitted, based upon a template prepared in WP6. • Work completed

- Use of resources
- Any deviations
- Impact and next steps

This will also be complemented by a short financial statement will also be submitted, guided by a template.

10. Call Budget Management

The Committee will be presented with the budget during each meeting, which will need careful monitoring. Care will be exercised to ensure the resources are **spread over the lifetime of the project**. It is planned that in the first 12 months only 30% should be spent. This includes effort for facilitation services. The budget will be reviewed after the first four meetings.

Annex 1: Evaluation Process

The RDA TIGER Selection Committee has prepared a process for evaluating the applications, with the following draft collection of metrics and criteria forming the basis for the development of the tools and processes used to select the proposals for funding.

It was understood that these metrics and processes represent an ideal approach that would maximise the theoretical fairness of the evaluation process. However, testing the evaluation process led to an observation that due to the large number of criteria and the time and effort needed for the evaluation, the results were unavoidably influenced by the external factors (available time, number of disruptions - such as phone calls or urgent messages - received during the evaluation). The complexity of the model also introduced non-intuitive or even inconsistent aspects¹³ to the model.

Thus, to ensure maximal fairness and transparency of the process in practice, the criteria will be adjusted and documented in the call texts (the evaluation criteria published in the first RDA TIGER call is included in Annex 3). However, the version below represents the ideals and aspirations underlying the evaluation process. Internal appraisal of the success of the process is a continuous WP6 process.

Principles of selecting these metrics:

1. Each criterion should be measurable - either qualitatively or quantitatively
2. Quantitative measures are considered preferable over qualitative - even if they are binary (Yes/ No)
3. Qualitative measures are sometimes unavoidable, but benefit from benchmarks or similar expected levels (e.g. if a certain behaviour or characteristic is present, it implies a certain score or rating).
4. Some criteria are usually *Go/ No Go* (cannot be approved if one of these are not satisfied).
5. The rest are aggregated as a score with possibly weighting
6. Objective is to reach more or less the same assessment outcome if the evaluators are different.
7. Processes should be transparent, and public
8. Mechanism for challenges to the outcome should be considered (e.g. include opinions from two extra evaluators, for example, using the same criteria, or all decisions are final)

¹³ As noted in the project review: For example, for the C1 criterion, a proposal that fulfils all tests (T1, T2, T3) will get the same grade as a proposal that fulfils only two tests and will have only a point difference with a proposal that does not fulfil any of the tests. Note also that C10 is not used in the Evaluation table."

Additionally, the original evaluation criteria would almost always fail in the E3 criteria.

A project that was not selected for funding can reapply, provided that:

1. All criteria are met, but the competition was too strong - next time improve score or rely on less competition
2. “Some criteria were not met, but please try again after improvements”

Principles and the Original Criteria

(In-kind: in-kind services, Sub MG: Subcontracts and minor grants (Travel, meetings), TPG: request to open a Third party grant)

#	Principle	Criterion	Metric	Benchmark	Grant Type		
					In kind	Sub MG	TPG
C1	Output	Output directly leads to a standard, recommendation, or methodology essential to FAIR implementation	$T_1+T_2+T_3$	$>1 \rightarrow 1^{14}$ $=1 \rightarrow 0$	Yes		
C2	Output	EOSC and SRIA Alignment	$T_{17-1}+T_{17-2}$	$=>1 \rightarrow 1$ $=0 \rightarrow 0$	Yes		
C3	Impact	Convincingly creates and advances knowledge and/ or expertise	$T_8 * [\max(T_{9-1}, T_{9-2}, T_{9-3}, T_{9-4}) + T_{10} + T_{12} + \max(T_{13-1}, T_{13-2}, T_{13-3}) + T_{14} + T_{15} + T_{16}]$	$>0 \rightarrow 1$ $=0 \rightarrow 0$	Yes	(yes)*	
C4	Implementation	Requested amount is within limits available	T_{20}	$=1 \rightarrow 1$ $=0 \rightarrow 0$	Yes	Yes	Yes
C5	Implementation and international connectivity	WG has clearly identifiable existing or potential members covering major European and non-European initiatives and experts relevant to the output creation.	$(T_4 * T_5)(T_6 + T_7)$	$=1 \rightarrow 1$ $=0 \rightarrow 0$	Yes		

¹⁴ The rationale of the evaluation criteria is to avoid creating incentives that would spread the focus across different goal domains. Conversely, the evaluation process will not penalise proposals that target more than one output category. The scope of the working group will also undergo community and TAB-reviews, both assessing the relevance of the outputs in a more in-depth manner.

C6	Diversity	The WG aim is novel and different from earlier supported actions	T ₂₅	Rating 0 .. 1	Yes		
C7	Implementation	Ability to deliver	T ₁₈ +T ₁₉	=1 → 1 =0 → 0	Yes		
C8	Impact of grant	Added value of the action to the WG outputs	T ₂₄	Rating 0..1		Yes	Yes
C9	Implementation	Eligibility	T ₂₁	=1 → 1 =0 → 0	Yes	Yes	
C10 ¹⁵	Grant applicability	Proposed Third party grant had clear statements of work and is easily applicable as a public call	T ₂₆	=1 → 1 =0 → 0			Yes

*) excellence of the WG for smaller grants can be obtained from earlier in-kind evaluations

Tests

#	Test	Description	Type	Method	Guidance
T ₁	Output Type	Output is a standard, methodology, recommendation	Binary	Yes = 1 No = 0	G1
T ₂	Essential to FAIR	Essential for putting FAIR principles into practice	Binary	Yes = 1 No = 0	
T ₃	EOSC Support	Supporting the development of the EOSC ecosystem	Binary	Yes = 1 No = 0	G2
T ₄	EU Initiative Member	Clearly identifiable existing or potential members covering major European initiatives	Binary	Yes = 1 No = 0	G3
T ₅	Non-EU Initiative Member	Clearly identifiable existing or potential members covering major non-European initiatives	Binary	Yes = 1 No = 0	G3
T ₆	Individual Expertise	At least one member is an expert in the field covered by the WG	Binary	Yes = 1 No = 0	G4

¹⁵ This eligibility criteria would be assessed separately and should included T21 in addition to T20. Failing either of these tests means that the proposal will not be taken further in the evaluation process, as even in case of a positive review result the proposed activity cannot be funded.

T ₇	Collective Expertise	Taken together, membership demonstrate expert cover of the subject covered by the WG	Binary	Yes = 1 No = 0	G4
T ₈	Outcome/ Contribution	Creates or Advances Knowledge	Binary	Yes = 1 No = 0	G5
T ₉₋₁	Research Output Beneficiation	Mechanisms and tools for creation of research output are present or created	Binary	Yes = 1 No = 0	-
T ₉₋₂		Mechanisms and tools for sharing of research output are present or created	Binary	Yes = 1 No = 0	-
T ₉₋₃		Mechanisms and tools for management of research output are present or created	Binary	Yes = 1 No = 0	-
T ₉₋₄		Mechanisms and tools for re-use of research output are present or created	Binary	Yes = 1 No = 0	-
T ₁₀	Cooperation	Facilitating scientific multidisciplinary cooperation	Binary	Yes = 1 No = 0	-
T ₁₂	Large Volume	Efficient handling or providing seamless access to large volumes of research outputs	Binary	Yes = 1 No = 0	G6
T ₁₃₋₁	Research Quality	Increasing FAIRness of scientific research outputs in EUROpe and globally	Binary	Yes = 1 No = 0	-
T ₁₃₋₂		Increasing openness of scientific research in EUROpe and globally	Binary	Yes = 1 No = 0	G7
T ₁₃₋₃		Increasing quality of scientific research in EUROpe and globally	Binary	Yes = 1 No = 0	G8
T ₁₄	Research Evaluation	Creation of more meaningful monitoring and research evaluation mechanisms	Binary	Yes = 1 No = 0	
T ₁₅	Improved Reproducibility	Enabling better reproducibility, validation of research outputs	Binary	Yes = 1 No = 0	
T ₁₆	Science Communication	Improving pathways for communication of science to the public	Binary	Yes = 1 No = 0	
T ₁₇₋₁	Advancing SRIA	Responding to at least one EOSC priority (e.g. in the EOSC Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda SRIA7 and its updates)	Binary	Yes = 1 No = 0	G9
T ₁₇₋₂	Pathway to EOSC or Open Science	Connecting via some other demonstrable pathway to the wider EOSC or Open Science needs.	Binary	Yes = 1 No = 0	G10

	needs				
T ₁₈	Ability	Perceived ability of the WG to produce the required tasks, determined by information on the past activities in RDA or the expected membership	Binary	Yes = 1 No = 0	G11
T ₁₉	Landscape Expertise	Related to the call text (e.g. RDA, EOSC, Open Science expertise)	Binary	Yes = 1 No = 0	G12
T ₂₀	Call amount	Request for the financial amount does not exceed the amount indicated in the open call.	Binary	Yes = 1 No = 0	G13
T ₂₁	Eligibility Test	Formally able to receive the financial support, i.e. able to provide necessary documentation and identification to fulfil the requirements for receiving grants in the call	Binary	Yes = 1 No = 0	G14
T ₂₂	Expertise - Consultants	Ability of the applicant to produce the required tasks, determined by information on the past consultancy or expertise	Binary	Yes = 1 No = 0	G15
T ₂₄	Impact to WG	Excellence of the proposed work, determined in reflection to the specification of the WG needs in the call text. What impact will the travel bring and is there a need for this particular travel	Fraction 0..1	Normalised aggregate	G17
T ₂₅	Lack of similarity to earlier supported WGs	The level the WG is novel and different from earlier WGs supported in the Action	Fraction 0.. 1	Normalise aggregate	G17
T ₂₇	Applicability as a public grant	The call requests is clear and easy to advertise and have clear indicators on how to prioritise potential call respondents.	Binary	Yes = 1 No = 0	

Guidance

#	Guidance
G1	Definitions of a standard, methodology, recommendation using existing outputs
G2	Definition of the EOSC Ecosystem
G3	Selection Committee maintains a list of qualifying initiatives, adding by consensus to the list as new initiatives are encountered

G4	Guideline for assessing expertise (publication record of members?)
G5	This test requires guidelines in respect of what qualifies as novelty, an advance, or an innovation
G6	What constitutes a large volume?
G7	How is openness or lack of it defined?
G8	Quality of process vs quality of content.
G9	SRIA objectives provided as a checklist
G10	Selection Committee maintains a list of qualifying needs or objectives, adding by consensus to the list as new items are encountered
G11	Guidance on how to interpret past performance in RDA or the general membership quality
G12	Ask applicants to list expertise matches, this will have to be defined in the call
G13	Clear call amounts for each type of grant for each call
G14	Required characteristics and documentation to be specified in the call
G15	Guidance on evaluating expertise of service providers (past projects, CV, ...)
G16	Aggregate of individual panel assessments - yes or no - based on CV, proposal, and WG Case Statement, normalised to a score between 0 and 1
G17	Aggregate of individual panel assessments - yes or no - based on proposal, and WG Case Statement, normalised to a score between 0 and 1

Evaluation

#	Aspect	Weight	Score		
			WGF	TPG	STG
E1	Excellence	50%	$(C1+C2+C3+C4)/4$	C5	C6
E2	Implementation	50%	C7	C7	C7
E3	Implementation	Go/ No Go	$C8+C9=2$	$C8+C9=2$	$C8+C9=2$

	on				
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Annex 2 Non-disclosure agreement template

Both the Selection Board members and any additional evaluators need to sign a non disclosure agreement on the content of the applications. The review results will be published for the successful applications (which terminates the confidential nature of the content via clause 1.5iv below), but for the non-successful applications the material is intended to remain undisclosed until the period specified in the NDA.

NON-DISCLOSURE AGREEMENT

THIS AGREEMENT [the Agreement] is entered into on this [insert number of day] day

of [insert Month and year] by and between:

1. RESEARCH DATA ALLIANCE ASSOCIATION AISBL, having its registered office or based in ETTERBEEK, BELGIUM, hereinafter referred to as the *Discloser* and
2. [Insert official name of the potential partner or participant], having its registered office or based in [insert the Legal Address of the Entity] hereinafter referred to as the *Recipient*

WHEREAS:

The Discloser and Recipient hereto entering into collaboration for the purpose of the Selection Board of the RDA TIGER project (funded under the Horizon Europe programme under project number 101094406), further detailed in the Grant Agreement of the abovementioned project. This collaboration includes the applications for support activities for RDA Working Groups and related Third party grants in context of this project, and information included in such applications.

Throughout the aforementioned discussions, the Discloser may share proprietary information or Confidential Information with the Recipient subject to the terms and covenants set forth below.

NOW IT IS AGREED AS FOLLOWS

1. Confidential Information

1.1 For the purposes of this Agreement, Confidential Information means any data or proprietary information of the Discloser that is not generally known to the public or has not yet been revealed, whether in tangible or intangible form, whenever and however disclosed within the RDA TIGER applications or other documents or discussions related to these applications, including, but not limited to:

- i. any scientific or technical information, invention, design, process, procedure, formula, improvement, technology or method;

ii. any concepts, samples, reports, data, know-how, works-in-progress, designs, drawings, photographs, development tools, specifications, software programs, source code, object code, flow charts, and databases;

iii. trade secrets; plans for products or services, and customer or supplier lists;

iv. Personal identity of applicants, or other people involved in the applications, including their contact information; or

v. any other information that should reasonably be recognized as Confidential Information by the Discloser or by the applicants of the RDA TIGER Third party grants or applicants of the other Working Group support actions.

1.2 The Discloser and the Recipient agree hereby that Confidential Information needs not to be novel, unique, patentable, copyrightable or constitutes a trade secret in order to be designated Confidential Information and therefore protected.

1.3 Confidential Information shall be identified either by marking it, in the case of written materials, or, in the case of information that is disclosed orally or written materials that are not marked, by notifying the Recipient of the confidential nature of the information. Such notification shall be done orally, by e mail or written correspondence, or via other appropriate means of communication.

1.4. In addition to specifically marked aspects in 1.3., all information provided in the RDA TIGER applications by the applicants are automatically considered to be Confidential information, unless specifically marked as non-confidential.

1.4 The Recipient hereby acknowledge that the Confidential Information proprietary of the Discloser has been developed and obtained through great efforts and shall be regarded and kept as Confidential Information.

1.5 Notwithstanding the aforementioned Confidential Information shall exclude information that:

(i) is already in the public domain at the time of disclosure by the Discloser to the Recipient or thereafter enters the public domain without any breach of the terms of this Agreement;

(ii) was already known by the Recipient before the moment of disclosure (under evidence of reasonable proof or written record of such disclosure);

(iii) is subsequently communicated to the Recipient without any obligation of confidence from a third party who is in lawful possession thereof and under no obligation of confidence to the Discloser;

(iv) becomes publicly available by other means than a breach of the confidentiality obligations by the Recipient (not through fault or failure to act by the Recipient);

(iv) is or has been developed independently by employees, consultants or agents of the Recipient (proved by reasonable means) without violation of the terms of this Agreement or reference or access to any Confidential Information pertaining to the Discloser.

2. Purpose of the Disclosure of Confidential Information

The Discloser and Recipient hereto entering into collaboration for the purpose of the Selection Board of the RDA TIGER project (funded under the Horizon Europe programme under project number 101094406), further detailed in the Grant Agreement of the above mentioned project. This collaboration includes the applications for support activities for Working Groups and Third party grants in context of this project, and information included in such applications.

3. Undertakings of the Recipient

3.1 In the context of discussions, preparations or negotiations regarding the activities of the Selection Board, the Discloser may disclose Confidential Information to the Recipient. The Recipient agrees to use the Confidential Information solely in connection with purposes contemplated in this Agreement and not to use it for any other purpose or without the prior written consent of the Discloser.

3.2 The Recipient will not disclose and will keep confidential the information received, except to its employees, representatives or agents who need to have access to the Confidential Information for the purpose of carrying out their duties in connection with the permitted purposes specified in clause 2.

3.3. The Recipient will inform them about the confidential quality of the information provided and will ensure that their agreement is obtained to keep it confidential on the same terms as set forth in this Agreement. Hence the Recipient will be responsible for ensuring that the obligations of confidentiality and non-use contained herein will be strictly observed and will assume full liability for the acts or omissions made for its personnel representatives or agents.

3.4 The Recipient will use the Confidential Information exclusively for the permitted purpose stated in clause 2 and not use the information for its own purposes or benefit.

3.5 The Recipient will not disclose any Confidential Information received to any third parties, except as otherwise provided for herein.

3.6 The Recipient shall treat all Confidential Information with the same degree of care as it accords to its own Confidential Information.

3.7 Nothing contained in this Agreement shall be construed as granting or conferring any rights to Confidential Information on the Recipient. Principally, nothing in this Agreement shall be deemed to grant to the Recipient a licence expressly or by implication under any patent, copyright or other intellectual property right. The Recipient hereby acknowledges and confirms that all the existing and future intellectual property rights related to the Confidential Information are exclusive titles of the Discloser. For the sake of clarity based in good faith, the Recipient will not apply for or obtain any intellectual property protection in respect of the Confidential Information received. Likewise any modifications and improvements thereof by the Recipient shall be the sole property of the Discloser.

3.8 The Recipient shall promptly return or destroy all copies (in whatever form reproduced or stored), including all notes and derivatives of the Confidential Information disclosed under this Agreement, upon the earlier of (i) the completion or termination of the dealings contemplated in this Agreement; (ii) or the termination of this Agreement; (iii) or at the time the Discloser may request it to the Recipient.

3.9 Notwithstanding the foregoing, the Recipient may retain such of its documents as required to comply with mandatory law, provided that such Confidentiality Information or copies thereof shall be subject to an indefinite confidentiality obligation.

3.10 In the event that the Recipient is asked to communicate the Confidential Information to any judicial, administrative, regulatory authority or similar or obliged to reveal such information by mandatory law, it shall notify promptly the Discloser of the terms of such disclosure and will collaborate to the extent practicable with the Discloser in order to comply with the order and preserve the confidentiality of the Confidential Information.

3.11 The Recipient agrees that the Discloser will suffer irreparable damage if its Confidential Information is made public, released to a third party, or otherwise disclosed in breach of this Agreement and that the Discloser shall be entitled to obtain injunctive relief against a threatened breach or continuation of any such a breach and, in the event of such breach, an award of actual and exemplary damages from any court of competent jurisdiction.

3.12 The Recipient shall immediately notify upon becoming aware of any breach of confidence by anybody to whom it has disclosed the Confidential Information and give all necessary assistance in connection with any steps which the Discloser may wish to take prevent, stop or obtain compensation for such a breach or threatened breach.

3.13 The Confidential Information subject to this Agreement is made available "as such" and no warranties of any kind are granted or implied with respect to the quality of such information including but not limited to, its applicability for any purpose, non-infringement of third party rights, accuracy, completeness or correctness. Further, the Discloser shall not have any liability to the Recipient resulting from any use of the Confidential Information.

3.15 The Discloser is not under any obligation under this Agreement to disclose any Confidential Information it chooses not to disclose.

3.16 Nothing in this Agreement shall be construed to constitute an agency, partnership, joint venture, or other similar relationship between the Discloser and Recipient.

4. Miscellaneous

4.1 Duration and Termination

4.1.1 This Agreement shall remain in effect until 2025-12-31. Notwithstanding the foregoing, the Recipient's duty to hold in confidence Confidential Information that was disclosed during the term shall remain in effect indefinitely, save otherwise agreed.

4.2 Applicable Law and Jurisdiction

4.2.1. This Agreement shall be construed and interpreted by the laws of Belgium. The court of Brussels, Belgium shall have jurisdiction.

4.3 Validity

4.3.1 If any provisions of this Agreement are invalid or unenforceable, the validity of the remaining provisions shall not be affected. The invalid or unenforceable provision shall be replaced by a valid and enforceable provision that will meet the purpose of the invalid or unenforceable provision as closely as possible.

4.4 Subsequent Agreements

Ancillary agreements, amendments or additions hereto shall be made in writing.

4.5 Communications

4.5.1. Any notices or communications required may be delivered by hand or e-mail, mailed by registered mail to the address of the Recipient/Discloser as indicated above. Any subsequent modification of addresses should be reasonably communicated in advance to the effect of this Agreement.

IN WITNESS WHEREOF, the Parties hereto have caused this Non-Disclosure Agreement to be executed as of the date stated above.

FOR [insert name] [insert name of representative]

[insert title]

Done at [place] on [date]

FOR [insert name] [insert name of representative]

[insert title]

Done at [place] on [date]

Annex 3: Published evaluation criteria in the first call

The published RDA TIGER call for applications used the following evaluation criteria:

The following criteria and weighting will be used to fairly and transparently evaluate the applications:

Criteria	Topic	Weighting as a percentage
Excellence (OS)	EOSC and OS connectivity	25%
Excellence (Impact)	Impact on the OS landscape	25%
Implementation	Implementation and international Connectivity	50%

